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Review Article

AN EXTENSIVE REVIEW OF PHYTOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF *VIGNA UNGUICULATA* PLANT

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Abstract:

Vigna unguiculata, a member of Fabaceae family and commonly referred to cowpea, a significant legume predominantly found in African and Asian regions. This plant has been traditionally utilized for various purposes, including disease management, livestock fodder, and human nutrition. The present review primarily highlights the conventional applications, pharmacological properties, phytochemical profile, and nutritional composition of *V. unguiculata*. Relevant data were gathered from leading scientific sources such as Science Direct, Springer Link and other Web sources.

Several bioactive compounds are identified in different parts of this plant, including Alkaloids, Phenolic compounds, Saponins, Fatty acids, Flavonoids, Carbohydrates, Vitamins, Amino acids, Carotenoids and Fibers.

These constituents exhibit a broad spectrum of pharmacological effects through in vitro, in vivo. For activities like as Antibacterial, Anticancer, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, Antidiabetic, Antiatherogenic, Antinociceptive, Anthelmintic. These pharmacologically active compounds may contribute to the plant's traditional medicinal applications, some of which remain unexplored.

In conclusion, *V. unguiculata* demonstrates remarkable pharmacological, nutritional, and phytochemical potential. Therefore, further in-depth studies are highly recommended to evaluate its clinical relevance and therapeutic applications.

Keywords: *Vigna unguiculata*, Phytochemistry, Pharmacology, Ethanopharmacology etc

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INTRODUCTION:

Since stoneage, we relied on plants to enhance chances of sustainability. Initially, their use was restricted to basic necessities like food, clothes, and shelter. Perhaps, as time passed, people began exploring other applications, leading a greater dependence on herbal remedies[1]. Plants have long been recognized for their significant contributions to human health. The knowledge of medicinal plant applications has been passed down through generations through a process of trial and refinement. Across the world, a vast number of species are traditionally used to treat various ailments. Globally, many developing nations, the lack of adequate healthcare facilities has led to a decline in the use of traditional medicine [2].

Herbal medicine practices involve the use of entire plants, specific plant parts, or isolated compounds with therapeutic properties[3]. The modern scientific pursuit of herbal treatments has revived interest in plant-based medicines that were discovered in previous centuries. Currently, nearly half of the pharmaceuticals in use are derived from natural sources [4]. The development of medicines is challenging due to money restrictions and lesser chances of success related to the drug discovery. Research in this field is evolving via simple assessments of different type of analysis methods [5].

After centuries of trial and error process, herbal research has created a place for itself as herbgenomics [6]. This emerging field integrates herbal medicine with genomic studies, bridging the gap between traditional practices and modern omics-based research[7]. Herbgenomics provides valuable insights into the genetic foundation of medicinal plants, enabling researchers to identify molecular mechanisms responsible for disease prevention and treatment [8].

This review focuses on the ethnobotanical, pharmacological, phytochemical, and nutritional aspects of *Vigna unguiculata*, a member of the Fabaceae family, to evaluate its therapeutic potential and explore future research directions [9].

Vigna unguiculata:

Fig. 1. Showing *Vigna unguiculata* plant

Vigna unguiculata L. Walp, commonly cultivated in dry, semi-arid, and subtropical climates, is an annual legume (Fig. 1). This species consists of two self-pollinating botanical species: as domesticated *V. unguiculata* var. *unguiculata* and the counterpart *V. u.u.* var. *spontanea*. Popularly known as cowpea or "lobia," this dicotyledonous leguminous plant which belongs to Fabales, family Fabaceae, subfamily Faboideae, tribe Phaseoleae, genus *Vigna*, and section *Catiang* [10]. This versatile crop is a vital food source for millions in tropical and subtropical regions, particularly in Africa (Nigeria, Burkina Faso, Kenya, Niger, Uganda, Tanzania, Ghana, Senegal, and Togo) and Asia (India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Bangladesh, Thailand, China, Malaysia, and Nepal). As an edible legume, it provides source for protein and nutrients to humans and animals though it's seeds and leaves[11]. Notably, it contains high levels of protein. The newbie leaves and pods are also utilized for the diet. With substantial amounts of carbohydrates, proteins, fiber, and fats, cowpea can complement cereals to meet human nutritional requirements. Due to its high mineral and vitamin content, it is often referred to as the "poor man's meat" in developing nations.

Morphology of *Vigna unguiculata* :

Cowpea is herbaceous plant with twin stems varies in structure, ranging from bushy to erect. Its leaves have petioles measuring between 2.5 and 12.5 cm in length [12]. The central leaflet, which is hastate and smooth, ranges in between 3 to 12 cm, whereas the leaflets shows asymmetrical nature. Flowers are arranged in axillary racemes on stalks measuring 15–30 cm in length. The pods, which are smooth, pendulous, and ranges in between 9 to 22 cm long, having 11 to 17 seeds and feature a distinctively curved tip [13].

Macroscopy of *Vigna unguiculata* seeds :

Seeds of *Vigna unguiculata* are kidney-sized, with wild as well as cultivated varieties exhibiting maculo-reticulate sculpturing within the seed coats. Though wild seeds appears typically grey, cultivated beans appear light-colored. The newly developed seeds are slightly compressed, ranging 4–7 mm in length, 4–6 mm in width, and 1.5–2.5 mm in thickness. Seed coating is smooth, firm, glossy and brown, with a micropyle located near the hilum, which itself measures 2–2.5 mm in length. As non-endospermic beans, they shows a storage tissue. Apart from the hilum area, the seed coat is relatively tough and thin. The cotyledons are fleshy and dicotyledonous, ranging 4-5 mm in length and 3.5-4.5 mm in width, with an incurved radicle of approximately 4 mm in length [14]

Ethnopharmacology of *Vigna unguiculata* :

Various parts of *V. unguiculata* contain beneficial phytochemicals that contribute to its nutritional value, use in animal feed, and medicinal applications. In Southern Africa, roots were consumed, while the scorched seeds rarely serve as alternative for caffeine. In Uganda, cowpeas commonly used in soups and the bean. It forms the mixtures like "moi-moi," "bean cakes"[15]. Traditional medicine practitioners boil the seeds with other plant roots to treat conditions such as hematuria and schistosomiasis [16]. Additionally, ground cowpea seeds mixed with oil are applied to persistent boils for treatment [17]. A decoction prepared from cowpea seeds and spices is considered an effective remedy against common cold [18]. The starch like gelatinous substance derived from cowpeas known as quench for thirst, while seeds, believed to have diuretic significance, used for strengthen the belly section. Furthermore, boiled seeds possesses anthelmintic property [19].

Cowpea leaves, seeds being used as a poultices to treat swelling and infections. Chewing the leaves is a traditional remedy for dental problems, while powdered carbonized seeds are applied to insect stings. In cases of snakebites, the roots serve as an

antidote. Additionally, cowpea is traditionally employed in treating discomfort in chest, dysmenorrhea, constipation, epilepsy. Some unknown part of plant used for sedation in tachycardia for their antinociceptive effects. In the treatment of amenorrhea, an oral infusion of the seeds is consumed, while powdered roots mixed with porridge are believed to alleviate chest pain, seizures, and menstrual discomfort. Cowpea leaves are also applied to burns and, when inhaled, are used as a remedy for headaches [20].

Phytochemistry of *Vigna unguiculata*:**Leaves of *Vigna unguiculata***

40 gm dried powder of *Vigna unguiculata* has been taken for performing the analysis with methanol (200 ml). It is prepared by the continuous extraction with soxhlate apparatus for 60°C to 3-4 hrs. Rotary evaporator was used to reduced the pressure for it's concentration. The extract was stored at 4°C in airtight container preliminary to GC-MS & LC-MS analysis. In detailed standard procedure of GC-MS & LC-MS has been followed to evaluate the phytochemical constituent present in the Leaves of *Vigna unguiculata* methanolic extract. [21]

Table 1: '+' shows the presence of constituent with increasing order.

Test	Leaves Extract
Flavonoids	+++
Alkaloids	+++
Terpenoids	+++
Saponins	+
Carbohydrates	++
Phenol	+++

Table 2: Phytochemistry of *Vigna unguiculata*

Sr. No	Probable compound	Retention Time (min)	Molecular formula	Nature of compound
1	Mephobarbital	7.28	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	Alkaloid
2	Syringic acid	16.56	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₅	Phenolic
3	P-hydroxybenzoic acid	12.77	C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	Phenolic
4	3-hydroxybenzoic acid	15.98	C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	Phenolic
5	Protocatechuic acid	8.75	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	Phenolic
6	Rutin	6.43	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₁₆	Flavonoid
7	Genkwanin	8.83	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₅	Flavonoid
8	Triparanol	1.01	C ₂₇ H ₃₂ CINO ₂	Terpenoid
9	Sapindoside A	10.98	C ₄₁ H ₆₆ O ₁₂	Saponin

Table 3: Phytochemical Constituents Reported in Different Parts of *Vigna unguiculata*

Plant Part	Major Phytochemicals	Methods of Detection
Seeds	Flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenolic acids	HPLC, GC-MS, UV-Vis
Leaves	Alkaloids, terpenoids, glycosides, steroids	Phytochemical screening, FT-IR
Pods	Phenols, flavonoids, carotenoids	HPLC, spectrophotometry
Roots	Tannins, saponins, coumarins	Standard qualitative tests
Whole plant extracts	Polyphenols, amino acids, fatty acids	LC-MS, chromatography

Seeds of *Vigna unguiculata*:

Vigna unguiculata contains high source of bioactive compounds which is responsible for the pharmacological properties and play a crucial role in disease prevention. Various investigations have identified numerous phytochemicals in *V. unguiculata* [22]. For instance, (HPLC-MS) evaluation of crude methanolic extracts has detected flavonols like quercetin and kaempferol, along with phenol compounds like gallic acid, protocatechuic acid, and coumarin acid [23].

● Quercetin ● Kaempferol ● Gallic acid
● Protocatechuic acid

Fig. 2. Phytoconstituents present in seeds of *Vigna unguiculata* by HPLC-MS analysis

Standard phytochemical screening of cowpea seeds following protocols established by Trease and Evans, and Sofowora, confirms availability of flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, saponins[24]. The seed extracted via Soxhlet apparatus using a n-hexane solvent mixture (3:1) were analyzed through High performance liquid chromatography, gas chromatography, thin-layer chromatography,

identifying triacylglycerols, unsaturated fatty acids, and sterols such as stigmaterol, avenasterol, campesterol, clerosterol and stigmaterol. Additionally, tocopherols were detected in the seed oil [25].

Further hydroalcoholic extraction of cowpea seeds revealed the presence of steroids, polyphenols, and glycosides. Ethanol-water (1:1) extracts obtained using pressurized liquid extraction at 170°C and analyzed via ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry (UHPLC-Q-TOF-MS) identified several phenolic acids and flavonols, including p-hydroxybenzoic acid, catechin, and dihydroxybenzoic acid[26]. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) & liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) analysis the cowpea leaves detects fatty acid esters like linoleic acid ester, stearic acid, palmitic acid ester, linoleic acid silyl ester along with essential oils, terpenoids[26].

Pods of *Vigna unguiculata* :

Phytochemical analysis of cowpea pods following the methodologies like Trease and Evans, Harborne, Sofowora, El-Olemyl et al., confirms presence of saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, resins, volatile oil, tannins, steroids, balsams, glycosides & terpenes [27]. Liquid chromatography-electrospray ionization-quadrupole and time-of-flight (LC-ESI-Q-TOF) analysis of macerated extracts identified quercetin, quercetin glycosides, and kaempferol diglucoside[28]. Ultra- performance liquid chromatography-quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry (UPLC-QTOF- MS) of cowpea seed coats further revealed flavonoids such as catechin, epicatechin, and delphinidin, phenolic acids, anthocyanins, fatty acids, sphingolipids [29].

Nutritional Composition:

An Ethanolic extracts containing cowpea seeds

analyzed using Ruhemann's procedure confirmed the presence of various amino acids, glutamine, threonine, aspartate, glycine, alanine, valine, cysteine, tyrosine, methionine, histidine, proline, leucine, phenylalanine, lysine, arginine, and tryptophan[30]. Starch analysis indicated content such as protein and ash. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis confirmed the polysaccharide nature of the resistant starch, suggesting its potential applications in food and microencapsulation [31].

Cowpea is known for its high folate content, particularly in seeds, which is essential for various biochemical processes. Protein content, determined

via the combustion method, ranged from 27% to 43% in leaves, 21% to 33% in dry grains, and 21% to 40% in immature pods, making it a valuable dietary protein [32]. Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICPOES) identified essential micronutrients from immature cowpea pods, including potassium, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, sodium, iron, manganese, boron, aluminum, zinc, and copper. High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) used for analysis of cowpea sprouts of carotenoid content showed lutein as the predominant component, followed by zeaxanthin and β -carotene, further highlighting its nutritional significance [33]

Table 4: Nutritional Composition of *Vigna unguiculata* Seeds

Nutrient Component	Concentration (Approx.)	Significance
Protein	20–30%	High-quality plant protein source
Carbohydrates	55–65%	Major energy contributor
Lipids	1–3%	Low-fat profile
Dietary Fiber	5–10%	Supports digestion & gut health
Minerals (Ca, Fe, Mg, Zn)	Varies by cultivar	Essential micronutrients
Vitamins (A, C, B-complex)	Trace to moderate	Antioxidant & metabolic roles

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF *VIGNA UNGUICULATA*:

Anthelmintic Activity:

The seeds of *Vigna unguiculata* (cowpea) were coarsely powdered and subjected to two different extraction methods: Soxhlet extraction using ethanol and maceration using chloroform-water. In a study to evaluate the anthelmintic properties of aqueous and ethanolic extracts, *Eisenia eugeniae* earthworms were employed as the model organism for protection to fight against intestinal worms. Different concentrations of extracts ranging from 10 to 100 mg/ml, were administered and observed for their anthelmintic effects, such as paralysis and worm death. The results indicated that both extracts were effective in causing paralysis and mortality in the worms at concentrations respectively 10 and 100 mg/ml. However, ethanolic extract demonstrated a stronger anthelmintic activity compared to the aqueous extract. For comparison, Piperazine citrate at 10 mg/ml were used for standard anthelmintic agent perhaps the distilled water was used for negative control. The research shows that *V. unguiculata* seeds possess considerable anthelmintic effects, with the ethanol extract outperforming the aqueous extract in potency.[34].

Antibacterial Activity:

The antibacterial activity of *Vigna unguiculata* was assessed against two types of bacteria: Gram-positive & Gram-negative of *Bacillus subtilise* & *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) respectively. The antibacterial testing was performed using the agar well diffusion method, with the extracts prepared in various concentrations (100, 200, and 300 μ g/ml). Tetracycline, a standard antibacterial agent, was also used at a concentration of 300 μ g/ml as a positive control [35]. The results indicates the antibacterial effects were extracts being dependent on their concentration. Notably, the aqueous extract exhibited the highest antibacterial activity at 300 μ g/ml against *E. coli*, producing a zone of inhibition by 21 mm. *B. Subtilise* was found to be less sensitive to the extracts compared to *E. Coli*. Additionally, the aqueous extract was more effective than the ethanol extract against both bacterial strains. Furthermore, the study highlighted that titanium dioxide nanoparticles synthesized from cowpea seeds were capable of inhibiting the growth of several bacterial strains, including:

- *Salmonella*,
- *E. Coli*,
- *Enterobacter*,
- *Serratia marcescens* and

➤ *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [36].

Another study investigated the antimicrobial potential of silver nanoparticles synthesized from porous starch extracted from cowpea. These nanoparticles shows slightly better antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Negative bacteria, with most potent effect observed with *E. coli* (inhibition zone of 18 mm) and the least against *Listeria monocytogenes* (6 mm). The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for these nanoparticles ranged from 5 to 16 µg/ml [37].

Antioxidant Activity:

Methanol was used to extract cowpea seeds from four cultivated varieties, and their antioxidant properties were evaluated through multiple assays, including FRAP, TRAP, ORAC, linoleic acid peroxidation, and radical scavenging tests [38]. The presence of phenolic compounds in these extracts contributed to strong antioxidant and antiradical activity. Specifically, *V. unguiculata* leaf extract exhibited notable free radical scavenging effects, for IC₅₀ value 61.04 ± 0.08 µg/mL, indicating its potency in neutralizing DPPH radicals [39].

Additionally, titanium nanoparticles synthesized from cowpea seeds demonstrated an ability to counteract oxidative stress-related diseases. Their antioxidant efficacy increased in proportion to the concentration of nanoparticles, highlighting their potential for biomedical applications [40]. Studies on protein hydrolysates from cowpea seeds indicated that trypsin-digested hydrolysates had the highest ferric reducing power, whereas both hydrolysates exhibited comparable hydrogen peroxide scavenging capacities. [41].

Further research on different cowpea seed extracts using in-vitro studies confirmed strong antioxidant activity through multiple assays, such as β-carotene-linoleic acid and ABTS+. A detailed HPLC analysis of the BRS Xiquexique cultivar identified significant amounts of phenolic compounds, particularly gallic acid and ferulic acid, which are well-known for their antioxidant properties [42]. Comparative studies of popular Indian legumes, including red and brown cowpea varieties, showed that cowpea exhibited the highest DPPH radical scavenging potential [43].

Moreover, investigations into the link between antioxidant potential and seed coat color in *Vigna unguiculata* concluded that darker pigmented varieties exhibited higher antioxidant activity. This suggests that breeding programs can enhance the antioxidant properties of cowpea by selecting deeply pigmented parental lines. Additionally, cowpea protein isolates hydrolyzed using alcalase at different pH levels (8.0 and 10.0) demonstrated improved antioxidant potential. The highest ORAC

activity was observed in peptides ranging from 1.8 to 6.5 kDa, emphasizing the role of protein hydrolysates in antioxidant applications [44].

Antinociceptive Activity:

The antinociceptive properties of cowpea were investigated using methanolic bean extracts, which were administered intraperitoneally in an acetic acid-induced pain model. The experiment showed that it helps significantly reduced abdominal contractions, indicating an analgesic effect [45].

Further investigations on *V. unguiculata* spp. *dekintiana* were conducted using thermal and chemical pain models on laboratory animals. Methanolic extracts and its different concentrations were tested for their ability to relieve pain through central and peripheral mechanisms [49]. In an in-vivo study using albino mice, the extracts were evaluated using acetic acid-induced writhing tests and hot-plate models. The findings concludes, At a dose of 400 mg/kg, the alcoholic extract significantly increased the reaction time in mice exposed to the hot plate, suggesting enhanced pain tolerance [46].

Moreover, fractionated plant extracts exhibited stronger pain-relieving effects than the crude extract, demonstrating higher potency. A dose-dependent reduction in the writhing reaction was also observed, confirming that the plant possesses bioactive compounds responsible for significant analgesic activity. These results support the traditional use of *V. unguiculata* subspecies *dekintiana* in pain management.

Antidiabetic Activity:

The potential of cowpea in diabetes management was explored by analyzing the effects of its seed oil on alloxan-induced diabetic animals. Administration of 200 mg/kg of cowpea seed oil for 21 days led to a notable decrease in plasma glucose levels, along with reductions in ALT, TC, TG, AST, LDL, and ALP [47]. Conversely, HDL levels were elevated, demonstrating the ability of cowpea seed oil to improve lipid profiles and potentially mitigate diabetes-related complications.

Further studies on *V. unguiculata* peptides revealed that they could activate Akt phosphorylation, a process essential for glucose metabolism and insulin signaling. This suggests that these peptides may help reduce hyperglycemia in diabetic individuals by enhancing glucose uptake in cells. In vitro research also investigated the inhibitory effects of cowpea protein hydrolysates and ultrafiltered peptide fractions (UFPF) on key enzymes linked to diabetes, including α-amylase, α-glucosidase, and DPP-IV [48]. The evaluation demonstrates, these cowpea-derived compounds

exhibited strong inhibitory activity, indicating their potential to slow down carbohydrate digestion and glucose absorption, which are crucial for managing postprandial blood sugar levels.

Additionally, studies on sorghum-cowpea composite biscuits assessed their impact on starch-hydrolyzing enzymes. The findings showed that these biscuits effectively inhibited α -amylase and α -glucosidase, suggesting that incorporating cowpea into functional foods may help control blood sugar spikes after meals [49].

Antiatherogenic and Hypocholesterolemic Activity:

Cholesterol-lowering effects of cowpea pods were examined using Wistar rats. Researchers analyzed key metabolic parameters, which includes serum total cholesterol level, triacylglycerides, non-HDL cholesterol, glucose levels. Results showed that rats administered cowpea had significantly lesser lipid and glucose concentrations contrast those on a regular basis diet, highlighting hypolipidemic and hypoglycemics benefits of cowpea [50].

Comparing different plant parts, cowpea seeds exhibited the highest hypolipidemic potential, followed by leaf extracts, both of which outperformed the standard cholesterol-lowering drug, Atorvastatin. Further in-vitro investigations explored the effects of peptide fractions derived from cowpea proteins during human digestion. These peptides exhibited strong inhibition of HMG-CoA reductase, the vital enzyme for the cholesterol synthesis, and also reduced cholesterol micellar solubilization, highlighting their cholesterol-lowering potential [51].

In an in-vivo study, protein isolates from cowpea sprouts were tested for their ability to regulate cholesterol levels in diabetic and healthy animals. The experiment concludes a decrease in blood triglycerides, cholesterol, LDL levels while increasing HDL, indicating that cowpea protein has promising cardioprotective properties. Another in vitro study investigated a specific peptide, Gln-Asp-Phe (QDF), derived from cowpea beta-vignin protein. This peptide exhibited strong inhibitory effects against HMG-CoA reductase, further reinforcing cowpea's potential for cholesterol management [52].

Additionally, flavonoid glycosides isolated from cowpea seed extracts using silica gel chromatography were tested for its tendency to prevent LDL oxidation levels [53]. The studies

evaluates, the compounds significantly reduced LDL oxidation, indicating their potential as antiatherogenic agents. This suggests that cowpea-derived flavonoids could play a crucial role in preventing atherosclerosis and other cardiovascular diseases [54].

Antimicrobial Activity:

The antimicrobial properties of cowpea seeds were studied, emphasizing bioactive peptides and amino acids. It exhibits the antifungal as well as the antiviral effects. Two proteins, termed α - and β -antifungal proteins, were isolated on the basis of their elution derivatives by CM-Sepharose column method. These amino acids demonstrated potent inhibitory effects against enzymes linked to HIV infection, such as HIV reverse transcriptase and α -glucosidase. Among various fungi tested, the α -antifungal protein exhibited the highest activity in most cases, although β -antifungal protein showed superior potency in one instance [55]. Both proteins also demonstrated inhibitory effects on cell-free translation, suggesting their potential use in antimicrobial treatments.

Methanolic extracts from cowpea leaves displayed strong antimicrobial activity in contrast to *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Candida albicans*. Additionally, extracts of Ethanol and Acetone from dual cowpea species, Bechwana White and Kpodjigu'égú'é, were tested against bacterial and fungal pathogens. Extracts shows effective inhibiting property for most of the fungi except for *Fusarium equiseti*, by 5.0 mg/ml concentration [56]. The Bechwana White extracts showed significant inhibition to *Alternaria alternata* for 2.5 mg/ml concentration, while *Fusarium proliferatum* was suppressed only by the ethanolic extract at the same concentration. In the case of Kpodjigu'égú'é, the acetone extract effectively inhibited *A. alternata* at 2.5 mg/ml, but neither ethanolic nor acetone extracts exhibited activity at lower concentrations (1.0 mg/ml) [57].

The Bechwana White acetone extracts was tested in contrast to Gram positive bacteria for antibacterial activity, which possesses *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterococcus faecalis*, showing inhibition at 2.5 mg/ml. Other bacteria, such as *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis* were inhibited at 5.0 mg/ml. Ethanolic extracts of Bechwana White shows antibacterial activity against *E. faecalis* and *E. cloacae* for the concentration 5.0 mg/ml. However, Kpodjigu'égú'é extracts did not show significant antibacterial effects [58].

Fig. 3. *Vigna unguiculata* showing antimicrobial effect mediated through modulation of different markers.

In another in-vitro study the two cysteine containing peptides (6.8 and 10 kDa) were expressed from cowpea pods which further tested against fungal pathogens *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Fusarium solani*, as well as the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. These findings suggest that cowpea seeds contain bioactive peptides with antifungal properties that may protect plants from infections.

Furthermore, seed oil from three cowpea varieties were treated against multiple Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria which includes :

- *Salmonella typhi*
- *Sarcina lutea*
- *Bacillus megaterium*
- *Shigella shiga*
- *Shigella sonnei*
- *Escherichia coli*
- *Bacillus subtilis*.

The oils exhibited antimicrobial activity against some of these bacterial strains. Among the tested fungi, cowpea seed oil was effective against *Mucor* spp., *Penicillium* spp. and *Candida albicans*. They were inactive in contrast to *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Findings from the above studies suggest that cowpea seed oil may be a natural source of antimicrobial agents for controlling pathogenic microbes [59]

Thrombolytic Activity:

An in-vitro thrombolytic study evaluated the clot-dissolving ability of cowpea seed extracts with vivid concentrations (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 mg/mL). The results shows significant dose-dependent thrombolytic effect, comparable to the standard drug streptokinase. This suggests that cowpea seeds possess natural thrombolytic properties, making them a potential candidate for clot-related

conditions [60].

Anticancer Effects:

Cowpea seed extracts were tested contrary to colorectal cancer cell lines (DiFi, E705, SW480), where they exhibited anticancer potential. Additionally, nanoparticles of titanium dioxide synthesized by seeds represents cytotoxic effects contrary to Mg-63 osteosarcoma cells [61].

Protein obtained by vivid cowpea cultivating species screened for their anticancer properties, alongside of Embu buff proving the most effective in reducing cell proliferation and inducing apoptosis in cancerous cells. This cultivar was found to be more effective against lung cancer than breast cancer [62].

Silver nanoparticles derived from porous starch extracts of cowpea were tested on cancerous and non-cancerous human cells using MTT and apoptosis assays. The studies concludes dose dependent cytotoxicity, highlighting their potential as a targeted anticancer drug delivery system.

Extracts from different cowpea plant parts, including seed coats and cotyledons, were also evaluated for anticancer properties. The free phenolic extract of whole seeds was particularly effective against hormone-dependent mammary cancer cells [63].

In another in-vitro study, L-asparaginase extracted from cowpea showed high cytotoxicity against HCT-116 and HEPG2 carcinoma cell lines, while demonstrating lower effectiveness against HELLA and MCF7 cell lines [64]. Additionally, an in-vivo study found that cowpea extract could inhibit breast cancer progression by downregulating PCNA and

upregulating BAX and BCL2, two key regulators

of apoptosis [65].

Fig 4. The various reported pharmacological activities of *Vigna unguiculata* highlight its therapeutic potential

Table 5: Pharmacological Activities of *Vigna unguiculata* Extracts

Extract Type	Biological Activity	Experimental Model
Ethanollic seed extract	Antioxidant	DPPH & ABTS assays
Methanolic leaf extract	Antimicrobial	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>
Aqueous seed extract	Antidiabetic	Alloxan-induced diabetic rats
Hydroalcoholic pod extract	Anti-inflammatory	Carrageenan-induced paw edema
Seed protein isolate	Nutritional & immunomodulatory	In vitro assays

CONCLUSION:

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*), a legume from the Fabaceae family, has both cultivated and wild varieties, offers significant nutritional as well as medicinal value. It is widely consumed in Africa (Nigeria, Kenya, Tanzania, Ghana, Senegal, etc.) and Asia (India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, China, etc.), providing essential nutrients and supporting health improvement.

Phytochemical studies identified alkaloids, fatty acids, phenolic acids, vitamins, amino acids, carbohydrates, steroids, carotenoids, flavonoids and fibers in cowpea, which contribute to its diverse pharmacological activities. Numerous experimental model studies confirmed its antioxidant, antidiabetic, antimicrobial, anticancer, thrombolytic, hypocholesterolemia, and

antinociceptive properties. However, more preclinical studies are required to identify active

compounds and understand their mechanisms before clinical trials can establish their effectiveness on living beings.

DENOUEMENT AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES:

This review offers a comprehensive and updated summary of the nutritional, medicinal, and pharmacological importance of *Vigna unguiculata*. *Vigna unguiculata* is not only a nutritious food source but also a reservoir of bioactive compounds responsible for its therapeutic potential.

Despite extensive studies on its antidiabetic and antimicrobial activities, there remains a need for further research to explore unverified traditional uses and identify active compounds. Future studies

should focus on standardizing bioactive compounds and conducting clinical trials to assess their real-world therapeutic applications.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this work.

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